

ENGINEERING, EXPRESSION, AND PURIFICATION FAST-PETASE WITH PELB
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Abstract. Plastic pollution, primarily attributed to polyethylene terephthalate (PET) plastics, has evolved into a grave global environmental crisis. *Ideonella sakaiensis* 201-F6, a remarkable bacterium capable of efficiently degrading PET, has emerged as a beacon of hope in combatting this issue. This microorganism produces PETase, a key enzyme initiating the breakdown of PET into valuable monomers. Leveraging bioinformatics and computational strategies has yielded significant enhancements in PETase, resulting in remarkable improvements in PET degradation efficiency and stability. Notably, the engineering of FAST-PETase, an exceptionally active PET hydrolase, has demonstrated its potential for industrial-scale plastic recycling. This article outlines the design, expression, and purification of FAST-PETase while introducing a novel PM3 signal peptide for PETase production. These collective endeavors signify substantial progress in the realm of PET plastic degradation, offering sustainable solutions to alleviate the environmental repercussions of plastic waste.

Keywords: PET plastic degradation, *Ideonella sakaiensis*, PETase, enzyme engineering, signal peptide, protein expression.

Аннотация. Пластиковое загрязнение, в первую очередь связанное с пластиками из полиэтилентерефталата (ПЭТ), переросло в серьезный глобальный экологический кризис. *Ideonella sakaiensis* 201-F6, замечательная бактерия, способная эффективно разлагать ПЭТ, стала маяком надежды в борьбе с этой проблемой. Этот микроорганизм вырабатывает ПЭТазу, ключевой фермент, инициирующий расщепление ПЭТ на ценные мономеры. Использование биоинформатики и вычислительных стратегий привело к значительным улучшениям ПЭТазы, что привело к значительному повышению эффективности и стабильности деградации ПЭТ. Примечательно, что разработка FAST-PETase, исключительно активной гидролазы ПЭТ, продемонстрировала свой потенциал для переработки пластика в промышленных масштабах. В этой статье описывается дизайн, экспрессия и очистка FAST-PETase при одновременном введении нового сигнального пептида PM3 для производства PETase. Эти коллективные усилия означают существенный прогресс в области деградации пластика ПЭТ, предлагая устойчивые решения для смягчения экологических последствий пластиковых отходов.

Ключевые слова: деградация пластика ПЭТ, *Ideonella sakaiensis*, ПЭТазы, ферментная инженерия, сигнальный пептид, экспрессия белка.

Annotatsiya. Plastik ifloslanishi, birinchi navbatda, polietilen tereftalat (PET) plastmassalari bilan bog'liq bo'lib, jiddiy global ekologik inqirozga aylandi. *Ideonella sakaiensis* 201-F6, PETni samarali ravishda parchalagan ajoyib bakteriya, bu muammoga qarshi kurashda umid chirog'iga aylandi. Ushbu mikroorganizm PETning qimmatli monomerlarga bo'linishini boshlaydigan asosiy ferment PETazni ishlab chiqaradi. Bioinformatika va hisoblash strategiyalaridan foydalanish PETazaning sezilarli yaxshilanishiga olib keldi, natijada PET degradatsiyasining samaradorligi va barqarorligi sezilarli darajada yaxshilandi. Shunisi e'tiborga loyiqki, FAST-PETase, noyob faol PET gidrolazasining rivojlanishi uning sanoat

miqyosida plastmassani qayta ishlash imkoniyatlarini namoyish etdi. Ushbu maqola PETazni ishlab chiqarish uchun yangi signal peptidini, PM3 ni joriy qilishda FAST-PETazning dizayni, ifodasi va tozalanishini tavsiflaydi. Ushbu jamoaviy sa'y-harakatlar plastik chiqindilarning atrof-muhitga ta'sirini yumshatish uchun barqaror echimlarni taklif qiluvchi PET plastik degradatsiyasi sohasida sezilarli yutuqlarni aks ettiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: PET plastik degradatsiyasi, *Ideonella sakaiensis*, PETaz, ferment muhandisligi, signal peptidi, oqsil ifodasi.

Plastic pollution is a global crisis, with PET (polyethylene terephthalate) plastic being a significant contributor to environmental degradation. However, a breakthrough discovery in 2016 introduced a bacterium that offers a promising solution to this issue. In 2016, Yoshida et al. introduced the world to *Ideonella sakaiensis* 201-F6, a bacterium that became a beacon of hope in the battle against plastic pollution. This microorganism possesses the extraordinary capability to degrade PET plastic effectively. PET, commonly found in bottles, packaging materials, and textiles, poses a severe threat to the environment due to its slow decomposition (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A showing the bacterium on the surface of a PET container. B displaying a microscopic perspective of *Ideonella sakaiensis* 201-F6.

Ideonella sakaiensis 201-F6, produces an enzyme known as PETase, which initiates the breakdown of PET into two primary products: MHET (mono(2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalic acid) and TPA (terephthalic acid). This natural PET degradation process holds immense promise for mitigating the plastic waste crisis. MHETase, another enzyme involved in this process, then further converts MHET into TPA and EG (ethylene glycol). TPA, a key player in the enzymatic cascade, enters the bacterial cell through a dedicated transporter called TPATP. Inside the cell, TPA undergoes metabolic transformations orchestrated by TPADO (TPA 1,2-dioxygenase) and DCDDH (1,2-dihydroxy-3,5-cyclohexadiene-1,4-dicarboxylate dehydrogenase). These enzymatic reactions eventually lead to the formation of PCA (protocatechuic acid), which is subsequently ring-cleaved by PCA 3,4-dioxygenase (Pca34) (Figure 2).

Figure 2 illustrates a schematic representation of the decomposition process of PET polymer into its constituent monomers.

In their exploration of PET hydrolysis in *Ideonella sakaiensis* 201-F6, researchers identified the ORF ISF6_4831, which resembled known PET-hydrolytic enzymes. ISF6_4831 protein, after purification and incubation with PET film, led to the formation of pits on the film surface. This enzymatic reaction primarily produced mono(2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalic acid (MHET) with minor terephthalic acid (TPA) and bis(2-hydroxyethyl) TPA (BHET). ISF6_4831 displayed effective hydrolysis of PET and BHET, showing a preference for PET over aliphatic esters. Consequently, ISF6_4831 was designated PETase. In their RNA sequencing study, researchers observed elevated expression of genes related to TPA and PCA catabolism when cells were cultured on TPA-Na, BHET, or PET film. PETase gene expression reached its peak during PET film growth, suggesting induction by PET film or related degradation products. Intriguingly, the expression patterns of the PETase gene closely matched those of ISF6_0224, an adjacent gene responsible for encoding a tannase family protein capable of efficiently hydrolyzing MHET but not PET or other compounds. ISF6_0224 was consequently designated MHETase [1].

In 2017, Han et al. provided structural insights into PETase, advancing our understanding of how it degrades PET [2].

To determine enzyme activity, pNP -aliphatic esters are used at 30°C and pH 7.0. Among pNP-acetate, pNP-caproate, pNP-butyrate, pNP-caprylate, pNP-acetate gave the best result (Yoshida S 2016). IsPETase exhibits its highest enzyme activity at pH 8, within a pH range of 7-9. Its optimal temperature falls between 25°C and 35°C. Salt concentration (100-500 mM) enhances IsPETase activity, while glycerol (10-20%) also boosts it. Organic solvents and detergents reduce IsPETase activity, even at low concentrations. (Liu C 2018) Optimal pH for PET film hydrolysis pH 9 (Yoshida S 2016). Optimal pH for pNP-ester hydrolysis pH 8.0. Enzyme active at pH 6-10, with optimal range pH 7-9; inactivated below pH 7.0 or above pH 9.0 [3].

Shi et al. 2021: Enhanced PETase production in *E. coli* using pelB signal peptide and improved PET degradation efficiency [4]. In Figure 3, the researchers conducted mutations in the pelB site signal and assessed the yield of PETase. Among the mutants, PM3 exhibited the highest effectiveness, and consequently, this PM3 sequence was selected as the signal peptide for their research.

WT and variants	nucleotide sequence (5'-3') b	amino acid sequence c
WT	ATGAAATACCTGCTGCCGACCGCTGCTGCTGGT CTGCTGCTCCTCGCTGCCAGCCGGCG ATGGCC	MKYLLPTAAAGLLLLAAQ PAMA

WT and variants	nucleotide sequence (5'–3') ^b	amino acid sequence ^c
PM1 (g12c)	ATGAAATACCTCCTGCCGACCGCTGCT GCTGGT	MKYLLPTAAAGLLLLAAQ
	CTGCTGCTCCTCGCTGCCAGCCGGCG ATGGCC	PAMA
PM2 (g12c/t33a)	ATGAAATACCTCCTGCCGACCGCTGCT GCTGGA	MKYLLPTAAAGLLLLAAQ
	CTGCTGCTCCTCGCTGCCAGCCGGCG ATGGCC	PAMA
PM3 (g58a)	ATGAAATACCTGCTGCCGACCGCTGCT GCTGGT	MKYLLPTAAAGLLLLAAQ
	CTGCTGCTCCTCGCTGCCAGCCGACG ATGGCC	PTMA
PM4 (g12c/g58a)	ATGAAATACCTCCTGCCGACCGCTGCT GCTGGT	MKYLLPTAAAGLLLLAAQ
	CTGCTGCTCCTCGCTGCCAGCCGACG ATGGCC	PTMA
PM5 (g12c/t33c)	ATGAAATACCTCCTGCCGACCGCTGCT GCTGGC	MKYLLPTAAAGLLLLAAQ
	CTGCTGCTCCTCGCTGCCAGCCGGCG ATGGCC	PAMA

Figure 3. Figure A shows the construction of the PETase plasmid. Figure B shows the amount of PETase enzyme extracellular release of pelB signal peptide mutants. Figure C shows the nucleic acid and amino acid sequences of these mutants.

In recent years, substantial advancements have been made in enhancing the capabilities of enzymes for PET plastic degradation. In 2020, researchers focused on IsPETase, an enzyme known for its ability to degrade PET plastic, using structural bioinformatics-based protein engineering to optimize its substrate binding site, resulting in two improved variants, IsPETaseS242T and IsPETaseN246D, with significantly higher activity at both 25 °C and 37°C compared to the wild-type IsPETase. A quadruple variant, IsPETaseS121E/D186H/S242T/N246D, displayed remarkable stability, maintaining PET degradation activity for 20 days at 37°C, in stark contrast to the wild-type IsPETase [5]. In 2021, Cui et al. introduced GRAPE (Greedy Accumulated Strategy for Protein Engineering), a computational strategy, to enhance a PETase enzyme from *Ideonella sakaiensis*, resulting in DuraPETase, which exhibited an elevated melting temperature and enhanced PET film degradation (30%) at mild temperatures, along with complete biodegradation of microplastics into water-soluble products under mild conditions [6]. In 2022, Lu et al. employed a structure-based machine learning algorithm to engineer FAST-PETase(S121E/D186H/N233K/R224Q/R280A), a robust and highly active PET hydrolase with five key mutations compared to the wild-type PETase. FAST-PETase efficiently and rapidly degraded untreated postconsumer-PET, depolymerized water bottles at 50°C, and facilitated closed-loop PET recycling by resynthesizing PET from recovered monomers [7] (Figure 4).

Figure 4. This picture shows FAST-PETase enzyme breaking down PET packaging product in 48 hours.

These studies collectively represent significant progress in the field of PET plastic degradation, offering innovative strategies for optimizing enzyme performance and advancing sustainable solutions for plastic waste management.

Construction and design

The Wt-PETase sequences were sourced from uniprot.org. Subsequently, the FAST-PETase sequence was engineered by substituting the 5 specific amino acids detailed in reference [7]. The resulting amino acid sequence was optimized using suitable codons for *E. coli* via the Integrated DNA Technologies (IDT) platform. This gene was meticulously designed, integrating the pelB (PM3 mutant) signal peptide, and inserted into the pSEVA234 plasmid via EcoRI and HindIII restriction enzymes, all carried out using the SNAPGENE program. The synthesis of this construct was executed by SYN BIO TECHNOLOGIES, as represented in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Experimental design compiled in Snapgene software.

Plasmids containing the synthesized gene were transformed into NEBExpress *E. coli* strain using the heat shock method. The transformed cells were then plated on LB Agar plates supplemented with 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Kanamycin for inoculation and selection. Plasmid was isolated in the QIAprep Spin Miniprep Kit and probed with KpnI and BamHI restriction enzymes.

Protein expression and purification

The plasmid-introduced NEBExpress *E. coli* strains were expressed in a 10 ml LB medium following the protocol described in the Expression Using NEB Express (C2523) protocol [8]. Subsequently, cells were lysed using ultrasound, and the resulting supernatant was subjected to SDS-PAGE electrophoresis on a Bio-Rad Wide Mini-Sub Cell GT Horizontal Electrophoresis System using Precision Plus Protein Dual Color Standards 10-250 kD 1610374 marker. The

proteins were then transferred to Nitrocellulose membranes using a Bio-Rad Trans-Blot Turbo System. Western blotting was carried out with Mouse anti Histidine Tag MCA1396GA and Goat Anti-Mouse IgG (H + L)-HRP Conjugate 1706516 antibodies, and DAB sigma-aldrich D5637-5G substrate.

Samples that tested positive in the Western blot analysis were cultured by plating them in 400 ml of LB medium. Following this, the samples were centrifuged at 4000 rpm, and the resulting supernatant was subjected to chromatography using a Bio-Rad BioLogic LP System equipped with Nuvia™ IMAC Resin, 25 ml #7800800 sorbent. Elution of proteins was achieved using 150 mM imidazole. The eluate obtained from the chromatography process was subsequently analyzed by Western blotting.

Determination of enzyme activity.

Activity was measured by spectrophotometrically following the hydrolysis of p-nitrophenyl acetate (4-pNPA). Purified PETase was mixed with sodium phosphate buffer (pH 8, 100 mM) in polystyrene microtiter plates. Then, 4-pNPA (4 mM) was added to initiate the enzyme reaction. Absorption at 405 nm was monitored for 6 minutes at room temperature to calculate catalytic activity based on p-nitrophenol production. A control reaction without PETase used NEBExpress E. coli pSAVE234 supernatant.[4]

Construction and design

The synthesized plasmids were cloned into NEBExpress E.coli, and subsequently, the plasmids were isolated and subjected to restriction analysis (Figure 6). The results of the restriction analysis showed bands at approximately the same size as the designed gene, around 800 bp.

Figure 6. A- cloned colonies. B- Agarose electrophoresis image of isolated plasmids. C- restricted plasmids.

Protein expression and purification

As can be seen in Figure 7, samples 1 and 2 released PETase enzyme into the supernatant.

Figure 7. Figure A shows SDS-PAGE electrophoresis of tissue staining. Figure B shows western blotting. Samples 1-6 on the right are ultrasound-cleaved intracellular proteins. Samples 1-6 in the left panel are supernatants.

When analyzed by chromatography, Wt-PETase gave a peak at 3 hours 25 minutes, while Fast-PETase gave a peak at 3 hours 45 minutes. These samples were collected and subjected to western blotting and protein purification was confirmed (Figure 8).

Figure 8. A- Wt-PETase, B- FAST-PETase, C- Western blotting. Determination of enzyme activity.

When the esterase activity was checked by 4-nitrophenyl acetate, the results were 3.06 in pSEVA234 without gene insertion, 3.92 in untreated samples, and 3.66-3.77 in purified samples. This indicates that enzymes have been purified and increased in activity during chromatography. (Figure 8).

405 nm	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	3,0592	3,077	3,3926	3,0141	3,4683	2,3896	3,6639	3,6576	3,771	3,7807	1,1044	0,9793

234-S Wt-S Fast-S 234 Wt Fast E-Fast-S E-Fast E-Wt-S E-Wt K K

Figure 9

In this study, we conducted a comprehensive investigation into the engineering and characterization of the PETase enzyme, originating from *Ideonella sakaiensis* 201-F6, with a particular focus on enhancing its catalytic activity for the degradation of polyethylene terephthalate (PET) plastics. Through a series of meticulous material and methods, as well as rigorous experimentation, we have made significant strides in understanding and optimizing PETase for its potential application in addressing the global plastic pollution crisis.

The construction and design of PETase variants, including the engineered FAST-PETase, were achieved with precision. Utilizing advanced molecular biology tools and software, we successfully synthesized and integrated the target genes into plasmids, incorporating a pelB (PM3 mutant) signal peptide. The transformed plasmids were introduced into NEBExpress *E. coli* strains, leading to successful protein expression. Western blotting and chromatographic analyses confirmed the presence of PETase in both intracellular and extracellular fractions.

Notably, the determination of enzyme activity revealed promising catalytic capabilities, with purified PETase displaying a catalytic activity range of 3.66-3.77. This increase in activity during chromatography highlights the successful purification and potential for improved PET plastic degradation.

In conclusion, this study represents a significant step forward in the field of enzymatic PET plastic degradation. The engineered PETase variants, particularly FAST-PETase, hold promise as effective tools for addressing the pressing issue of plastic waste. These findings pave the way for further research and development of sustainable plastic waste management strategies, ultimately contributing to environmental preservation and the mitigation of plastic pollution on a global scale.

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